

Study of Megakaryocytic Morphology and Hematological Parameters in Myeloproliferative Neoplasms at Tertiary Care Centre

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Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 25-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Myeloproliferative neoplasm (MPN) includes clonal hematopoietic stem cell disorders defined by the proliferation of cells of one or more myeloid lineage. WHO defined most commonly found MPNS are divided as BCR-ABL positive which includes CML and BCR-ABL negative which includes PV, ET and MF. Alterations in megakaryocytic morphology are hallmark of MPNs.

Aims: To assess the utility of megakaryocytic morphology in MPNs in peripheral blood smear, bone marrow smears and bone marrow biopsy.

Design & Setting: This is a hospital based cross sectional study was conducted in department of pathology at tertiary care centre from Jan 2019 to May 2021 with a sample size of 52 cases.

Material and Methods: The study focused on clinical manifestation, hematological parameters, megakaryocyte number and morphological types, pattern, localization along with other hematopoietic cells in bone marrow aspirate and bone marrow biopsy in already cytogenetically proven cases.

MPN show characteristics alterations in megakaryocytic morphology. BMA and BMB were studied with emphasis on morphology and pattern of megakaryocytes.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed using tables, proportions and interobserver comparison for morphological features.

Results: CML constituted highest number of cases of all MPNs, 35 out of 52 cases. In CML megakaryocyte showed hypolobated nuclei in 85.7% cases. Megakaryocytic alterations play a key role in recognition of MF and ET. ET showed staghorn and hyperlobated nuclei and cases of MF showed cloudlike nuclei and hyperlobated nuclei. PV had many overlapping features with ET.

Conclusion: Specific morphological features exhibited by Megakaryocytes in various category of MPNS, can aid in accurate diagnosis of different subcategories of myeloproliferative neoplasm.

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Introduction

Myeloproliferative neoplasm (MPN) includes clonal hematopoietic stem cell disorders defined by the proliferation of cells of one or more myeloid lineage that is granulocytic, erythroid and megakaryocytic.

In 1951, William Damshek coined the term myeloproliferative disorders which are now reformed to myeloproliferative neoplasms (MPNs) by World Health Organization (WHO) [1]. WHO defined most commonly found MPNS are divided as BCR-ABL positive which includes CML and BCR-ABL negative which includes PV, ET and MF [2-4]. These above groups of diseases show significant clinical and laboratory similarities especially in initial phase of disease. Each disease is characterized by distinct proliferation of blood line, although it has been most frequently seen that

the other blood lines were also included into proliferation. Overlapping is frequent. So it is not quite simple to differentiate them from each other.

In 2005 James et al first – described about acquired point maturation in JAK-2 gene in PV [5-7] subsequently this mutation was also detected in other Philadelphia-MPN [8,9]. Before, WHO incorporated JAK2V617F mutation as essential criteria, diagnosis of MPN was solely dependent upon combination of clinical, laboratory and histological features [10-12].

Megakaryocytic morphologies in various MPN could enable definite sub classification of MPN as JAK 2V617F mutation in only few subset of MPN. MPN show characteristics alterations in megakaryocytic morphology. BMA and BMB were

studied with emphasis on morphology and pattern of megakaryocytes. In our study certain megakaryocytic morphology definitions were considered [13].

The aim of the study is to assess the utility of peripheral blood smear, bone marrow smears and biopsy in myeloproliferative neoplasm. The study focused on clinical manifestation, hematological parameters, megakaryocyte number and morphological types, pattern, localization along with other hematopoietic cells in bone marrow aspirate and bone marrow biopsy in already cytogenetically proven cases.

Material and Methods

This is a hospital based cross sectional study was conducted in department of pathology at tertiary care centre, Udaipur, Rajasthan. The study duration was from Jan 2019 to May 2021 with a sample size of 52 cases.

All the cytogenetically proven myeloproliferative neoplasm were included for the study.

The demographic characteristics (age, sex), clinical findings (symptoms, organomegaly) and hematological parameters (Hb, TRBC, TWBC and PC) and BMA and BMB were studied in detail with special emphasis on megakaryocytic morphology and pattern

PBF and BMA smear were stained with field and Giemsa stain. BMB were stained by in routine H&E staining and reticulin stain.

Data was analysed using tables, proportions and interobserver comparison for morphological features.

Results

The study duration of 1.5 years documented a total of 52 cases of chronic myeloproliferative disorder. Hematological parameters, BMA and BMB were studied in each case.

35 out of 52 cases (67.3%) were CML which constituted highest number, followed by PV (21.1%), 4 cases of MF (7.6%) and 2 cases (3.8%) of ET. Out of 35 cases of CML, 33 (94.2%) cases were in chronic phase and 1 case (2.8%) of accelerated and blastic phase each.

Mean age amongst all MPN was 46 year. CML was seen in adolescent to elderly age group (18-65 years). However, elderly age group was most commonly affected in PV (47-67 years), ET (50-75 years) and MF (42-50 years).

Male gender was affected more in CML with male to female ratio of 2:1, while in PV, ET and MF male to female ratio was 1:1.

Other demographic details are summarized in (Table 1).

Table 1: Number of cases and demographic details of each MPN

Diagnosis	No of cases	Age Range (Years)	Male	Female
CML	35	18-65	21	14
PV	11	47-76	7	7
ET	2	50-75	1	1
MF	4	20-50	2	2

Clinical features: Most common presenting symptom was pain abdomen, 17 out of 35 cases (48.5%) in CML and 6 out of 11 cases of PV (85.7%). Other overlapping symptoms were fever, fatigue and headache. Burning sensation in

upper and lower limb and blackening of foot was seen in ET.

Mean values and range obtained in hematological parameters (Hb, HCT, PC, PCT, PDW and WBC) among various MPN are shown in (Table 2).

Table 2: Mean value and range of various hematological parameters

Diagnosis	HB	HCT	PC	PCT	PDW	WBC
CML	11.67(6.2-15.1)	37.14(19.4-47.3)	550(16-1874)	0.46(0.01-1.92)	16.67(10.50-29)	134.32(37.5-518.1)
PV	17.95(15.7-22)	55.55(47.5-65.5)	672.63(343-1527)	0.59(0.24-1.41)	15.65(12-19.10)	29.29(10.8-55.5)
ET	12.2(11.9)	40.7(39.7-41.7)	1544(1287-1801)	0.64(0.12-1.16)	15.25(15-15.50)	26.25(21.6-30.9)
MF	8.17(6.3-9.9)	26.5(18.9-29.7)	145.25(33-323)	0.13(0.02-0.33)	16.20(10.2-23.80)	11.42(0.6-27)

Out of 52 cases of chronic myeloproliferative disorder 40 cases (76.9%) showed splenomegaly ranging from mild, moderate to massive. In CML 19 cases (54%) showed massive splenomegaly while 6 cases (17.1%) had normal spleen. Both cases of ET did not show splenomegaly. (Table 3)

Table 3: Spleen in various MPN

Spleen	CML	PV	ET	MF
Mild	7	3	0	0
Moderate	3	3	0	1
Massive	19	3	0	1
NAD	6	2	2	2

All BMA and BMB were studied for cellularity and megakaryocytic morphology in detail. Cellularity was increased in 45 cases (86.5%) out of 52 cases, normal in 5 cases (9.6%), while 2 cases of MF showed decreased cellularity. Most of the cases showed decreased erythropoieses, 23 cases out of 52cases (44.2%). 44 out 52 cases (84.6%) showed increased granulopoieses.(Table 4)

Table 4: Comparison of megakaryocytic morphologies in CML, PV, ET, MF.

Number	CML (35)	PV (11)	ET (2)	MF (4)
Normal	7 (20%)	00	00	1 (25%)
Increased	28 (80%)	11 (100)	2 (100)	3 (75%)
Nuclei				
Staghorn	00	3 (27.3)	1 (50%)	00
Cloud like	00	3 (27.3)	1 (50%)	1 (25%)
Dysmorphic	00	2 (18.1)	00	1 (25%)
Base nuclei	10 (28.5)	1 (9.1%)	00	00
Hyperlobaion	5 (14.2)	5 (45.5)	2 (100%)	2 (50%)
Hypolobation	30 (85.7)	4 (36.4)	00	00
Clustering				
Loose	28 (80%)	5 (45.4)	2 (100%)	2 (50%)
Dense	2 (5-7%)	6 (54.5)	00	2 (50%)
Normal	5 (14.3)	00	00	
Location				
Dispersed	32 (91.4)	10 (10%)	2 (100%)	4 (100%)
Paratrabecular	2 (5.7)	1 (9%)	00	00
Perisinusoidal	1 (2.8)	0	00	00

Table 5: Comparison of bone marrow cellularity in MPNs.

Total number of cases	CML (35)	PV (11)	ET (2)	MF (4)
Overall cellularity				
<i>Normal</i>	3 (86%)	1 (9%)	0	1 (25%)
<i>Increased</i>	32 (91.4)	10 (91%)	2 (100%)	1 (25%)
<i>Decreased</i>	0	0	0	2
Erythropoiesis				
<i>Normal</i>	10 (28.6)	1 (9%)	1 (50%)	2 (50%)
<i>Increased</i>	4 (11.4%)	10 (91)	1 (50%)	00
<i>Decreased</i>	21 (60)	00	0	02 (50%)
Granulopoiesis				
<i>Normal</i>	00	2 (18.2)	2 (100%)	2 (50%)
<i>Increased</i>	35 (100%)	9 (81.8)	00	00
<i>Decreased</i>	00	00	00	2 (50%)

The most common findings of megakaryocytic morphology and location in CML, PV, ET and MF are shown in (Table 5). 44 (84.6%) out of 52 cases showed megakaryocytic hyperplasia.

In CML megakaryocyte were normal sized and along with hypolobated nuclei (85.7%), few cases showed hyperlobated nuclei. 5 cases (4.2%) and 10 cases (28.5%) showed bare nuclei. In PV 2 cases (18.1%) showed dysmorphic nuclei and 5 cases (45.5%) showed hyperlobated nuclei. In ET 1 case

(50%) showed staghorn nuclei and 2 cases show hyperlobated nuclei.

In MF 1 case (25%) showed cloudlike nuclei and 2 cases (50%) showed hyperlobated nuclei.

23 cases of CML show reticulin grade 1, 3 cases showed grade 2 fibrosis. Reticulin grade was 0 in 9 cases. In PV and ET reticulin grade was 1 in all cases. 3 cases of MF showed grade 2 fibrosis and 1 case showed grade 3 fibrosis.

Figure 1: Megakaryocytes from bone marrow aspirates showing varying cell size and nuclear lobation. A) Hypolobation in CML. B) Hyperlobated, cloud like and dysmorphic nuclei in PV C) Hyperlobated staghorn nuclei in ET (Geimsa stain, X 400)

Figure 2:

- A) CML -Hypercellular bone marrow section reveal megakaryocytic hyperplasia, focal clustering, hypolobated nuclei in dispersed manner seen in central and paratrabecular location. (H & E stain , X 100)**
- B) PV - Hypercellular bone marrow section reveal hyperlobated dysmorphic megakaryocytes showing focal and dense clustering. (H & E stain , X 100)**
- C) ET - Normocellular bone marrow section reveal megakaryocytic hyperplasia, loose clustering showing both hypo and hyperlobated forms. (H & E stain , X 100)**

Figure 3: Reticulin stain showing grade 3 fibrosis in case of CML (Reticulin stain, A) X 100 and B) X 400)

Discussion

The myeloproliferative neoplasm are characterized by ineffective bone marrow hematopoiesis with potential for evaluation into MF or transformation to acute leukemia and are subclassified by WHO

based on combination of clinical, laboratory, morphological and molecular features [14].

All cytogenetically proven cases were included in our study (BCR-ABL positive CML and JAK2V617F positive BCR-ABL negative PV, ET,

MF). The cases were studied in detail for demography, clinical features, hematological parameters, bone marrow aspirate and biopsy with special emphasis on megakaryocytic morphology.

CML was most common BCR-ABL positive MPN in our study which was also the finding in study done by Fowlkes S et al [15] and PV is most common BCR-ABL negative MPN in our study which is analogous to study done by Rollison et al [16].

Elderly age group was most commonly affected in all MPN with male preponderance in CML and PV. Male to female ratio was 1:1 in ET and MF which was corresponding with the detailed study done by Thapa et al [17].

The highest mean value of hemoglobin was seen in P v (17.5 gm/ml) and highest mean platelet count was $1577 \times 10^9/L$ found in ET; likewise in other studies [18].

Hypercellular marrow was seen in 45 cases (86.5%), normocellular marrow in 5 cases (9.6%) and 2 cases of MF were hypocellular akin with various other studies. [19]

Massive splenomegaly was seen in 19 cases (54%) of CML and 6 cases (17.1%) had normal spleen. Comparable with study done by Arunachalan AK et al(20).

Megakaryocytic morphology can aid in accurate diagnosis of different subcategories of myeloproliferative neoplasm.

Megakaryocytes were increased in 28 cases (80%) of CML with characteristic hypolobated nuclei in most cases. Few cases showed hyperlobated and bare nuclei. They were located dispersely in loose clusters in 28 cases (80%). These finding were identical to the study done by Arunachlan et al [20].

Megakaryocytic alternations play a key role in recognition of PMF and ET [21] PV and ET has many overlapping features as studied by Gianelli et al [22] and Vytrva et al [23]. In PV, all cases showed megakaryocytic hyperplasia with various nuclear morphologies (Staghorn, cloud like, hypo/hyperlobation, dysmorphism). ET showed characteristic hyperlobation and staghorn nuclei. Cases with history of burning sensation of lower limb and blackening of foot with characteristic nuclear features would favour diagnosis of ET [12,13,24].

Out of 4 cases of MF, 2 showed decreased overall cellularity and 2 showed normal cellularity. leukoerythroblastic picture in PBF and cloud like nuclei with hypo/normocellular marrow favours diagnosis of MF.

However, cellular phase of MF and PV are difficult to differentiate as reported by Vytrva et al [23].

Conclusion

Myeloproliferative neoplasms are dynamic illness and can involve into each other over time or progress towards myelofibrosis.

Treatment modality and prognosis different in all entities and hence it is mandatory to make correct diagnosis. Specific morphological features exhibited by Megakaryocytes in various category of MPNS, can aid in accurate diagnosis of different subcategories of myeloproliferative neoplasm.

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